

GENERAL STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT OF CHINA'S "ONE BELT, ONE ROAD" PROGRAM

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the development history, general structure, and important aspects of the "One Belt, One Road" program, which is considered the most progressive country in the current global development era, and which can serve as an example for other countries. Also, the economic and socio-political significance of some countries, which are considered members of the prospective program based on legal documents, were also analyzed. The authors of many local and foreign researches were studied on the topic of our research. The main content of the studied literature is that the opportunities for exporting products and services produced by the member countries of this program promoted by China have been significantly improved, and the number of days spent on exporting products and services has almost halved. Forecasting and statistical research methods were actively used in the research, mainly using official statistics of the last 10 years provided by the country of China. And at the end, conclusions and suggestions are given regarding this article, and this research is completed with a list of used literature.*

Keywords: *China, "One Belt, One Road", economy, transport, export and import, transport corridors, economic growth, OBOR.*

Introduction

The "One Belt, One Road" vision program, now known as OBOR, was first officially announced in 2013 by Chinese President Xi Jinping. The core of this program is a global infrastructure development strategy aimed at investing in more than 150 countries and international organizations. The initiative includes six infrastructure corridors linked by road, rail, energy and digital infrastructure, as well as a maritime silk road linked through port development.

This perspective is the origin of the program. Chinese President Xi Jinping presented the OBOR initiative as the "Silk Road Economic Association" for the first time during his visit to Kazakhstan in September 2013. The term *Makon* describes the recommended overland routes for transport and rail logistics through Central Asia along historical trade routes. The term «Road» refers to the 21st century Maritime Silk Road, which includes sea routes through Southeast Asia to South Asia, the Middle East and Africa.

The main objectives of this perspective program are to create a single large market through the use of international and domestic markets. Through cultural exchange and integration, it aims to strengthen mutual understanding and trust among member states. The initiative seeks to create innovative models of capital flows as well as technological databases to stimulate economic growth across regions.

While proponents point to the potential economic benefits of the BRI in terms of trade flows and GDP growth in participating countries, critics argue that it poses risks such as disproportionate debt burdens for some participating countries. The initiative has sparked active debate about its implications for global geopolitics and economic development.

The practical visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the People's Republic of China on April 24-27, 2019 to participate in the work of the second international forum "One

Belt, One Road” was an important step in strengthening the reputation of our republic in the international arena. The initiatives put forward during the forum were fully supported by the world community and they open wide prospects for Uzbekistan in promoting priority programs and projects for the national economy.

Figure-1: Strategic map of China’s “One Belt, One Road” perspective program.

The “One Belt, One Way” initiative, aimed at improving the cooperation of the member countries of the program, is related to the specific provisions of the action strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. It will also contribute to the consistent development of comprehensive Uzbek-Chinese strategic partnership relations in industry, energy, infrastructure development, transport, logistics, agriculture, tourism, education and other areas.

In conclusion, China’s Belt and Road Initiative represents a significant effort to strengthen regional connectivity through large-scale infrastructure investments across multiple continents.

Literature review

Undoubtedly, China’s “One Belt, One Road” perspective program can further develop the export and import potential of countries and stimulate economic growth in the country by connecting the global transport corridors.

A number of research scientists related to this topic, in particular P.Irina, R.Aoyama, M.Krukowska, M.Sarker, K.Haggai conducted their scientific research. Also, our local researchers such as J.Jabborqulov, U.Habibjonov, N.Axmadjonov and U.Ayjun also conducted their scientific research related to our work.

According to the general opinion of the researchers, the perspective is an important opportunity for the countries within the program to increase their trade flows, reduce global trade costs and increase their domestic production capacity. As a result of the studies, it should be noted that the program increases the volume of global trade by 3.9% and reduces global trade costs from 2.4% to 1.3%. It can also increase the GDP of developing countries in Asia and Africa by an average of 2.9% to 4.3%.

According to a number of opinions expressed by the researchers about the “One Belt, One Way” program, the goals of this program are mainly divided into 5 types. These are:

- strengthening global trade;
- ensuring economic growth;
- promotion of cultural exchange;
- facilitating technology transfer;
- eliminating disparities in development.

Projections show that by 2041, the OBOR analysis will increase global GDP by \$6.9 trillion annually.

Research Methodology

In the methodology of our research on the general structure and development of China’s “One Belt, One Road” perspective program, we actively used several research methods, in particular comparative analysis and induction-deduction research methods. This type of research includes steps such as: defining the main research hypothesis, choosing the most optimal and currently relevant countries for comparison, collecting statistical data, and analyzing the collected data.

In the first part of our study, general brief information about the article was given. In the second part, the introduction of the article, in the third part, the literature analysis and research methodology were formed. Also, in the following parts of our research, a statistical analysis will be carried out on the general structure of the “One Belt, One Road” perspective program, the general classification of its member countries, and their place in the country’s economy. And finally, as a result of the analysis, conclusions and suggestions are given, the list of used literature is given, and the research is completed.

Analysis and results

Since the launch of the «One Belt - One Road» initiative, China and 5 countries of Central Asia have further expanded cooperation and achieved a number of historic results. In particular, in the first quarter of 2023, China’s trade with the countries of Central Asia increased by 37.4 percent. In 2022, trade will increase 100 times compared to thirty years ago and will reach 70.2 billion dollars. The lack of a direct access to the sea has been a limiting factor for further expansion of Uzbekistan’s foreign economic activities and product exports. In this regard, our government has been promoting the initiative of building a railway through Afghanistan to Pakistan’s Gwadar port for the past years. This initiative is also reflected in the « One Belt - One Road » project. One of the challenges in expanding railway infrastructure in the One Belt - One Road project is the difference in railway standards. In particular, the distance between railway tracks is 1676 mm in countries such as India, Spain, Argentina, Chile; 1520 mm in Russia, Uzbekistan and similar post-Soviet countries; 1435 mm in the USA, Canada and most European countries; It is 1067 mm in Japan, Indonesia and many countries of South and East Asia.

The OBOR program focuses on connecting China with the following economic corridors:

- Europe through Central Asia and Russia;
- Middle East through Central Asia;
- Ports in Southeast Asia, South Asia and the Indian Ocean;
- MRS focuses on connecting PRC coastal ports with;
- Europe through the South China Sea and the Indian Ocean;
- South Pacific through the South China Sea.

The corridors of the program connecting Asia, Europe, Africa and the Middle East cover more than 50 countries belonging to five regions with a total population of 4.1 billion and a gross domestic product of more than 16 trillion dollars in 2019.

Table-1.

Countries included in the perspective program “One belt, one road”.

Continents	Countries in the program area
Central Asia	Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan
Mongolia and the Russian Federation	Mongolia and the Russian Federation
Southeast Asia	Vietnam, Cambodia, Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, Indonesia, Darussalam, Philippines, Myanmar,
South Asia	India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Afghanistan, Nepal, Bhutan, Sri Lanka, Maldives
Middle East and Europe	Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, Romania, Bulgaria, Serbia, Montenegro, Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, Estonia, Lithuania, Latvia, Ukraine, Belarus, Moldova
Western Asia and the Middle East	Turkey, Iran, Syria, Iraq, United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Bahrain, Kuwait, Lebanon, Oman, Yemen, Jordan, Israel, Armenia, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Egypt

The fact that our country does not have direct access to international seaports is one of the factors that hinders the development of its transport logistics. Today, participants of foreign economic activity engaged in international cargo transportation are using the following transport corridors:

Corridor 1: in the direction of the ports of the Baltic states (with transit through Kazakhstan and Russia) - Klaipeda (Lithuania), Riga, Liepaja, Ventspils (Latvia), Tallinn (Estonia);

Corridor 2: through Belarus and Ukraine (with transit through Kazakhstan and Russia) to Chop (Ukraine) and Brest (Belarus) border crossings, then to Europe;

Corridor 3: to the Ukrainian port of Ilichevsk (with transit through Kazakhstan and Russia), with exit to the Black Sea;

Corridor 4: to the Georgian ports of Poti and Batumi (with transit through Turkmenistan and Azerbaijan), with access to the Black Sea, named the TRACEKA Corridor;

Corridor 5: Iran’s Bandar-Abbas port (Turkmenistan in transit) with exit to the Persian Gulf;

Corridor 6: East through China (with transit through Kazakhstan) to the Yellow Sea;

Corridor 7: In the eastern direction through the ports of Nakhodka and Vladivostok of the Far East (with transit through Kazakhstan and Russia) to the Yellow Sea;

Corridor 8: to Turkey and Europe (through Turkmenistan and Azerbaijan with transit on the new Baku-Akhalkalaki-Kars railway).

The PRC country accounts for about 32% of the program's population and about 40% of its GDP. There are sufficient disparities between the per capita incomes of prospective program countries, and a number of countries located along the program corridors are still backward countries. These are 8 low-income economies (per capita income below \$1,025), 15 lower-middle-income economies (per capita income between \$1,025 and \$4,025); 15 are classified as upper-middle-income (\$4,025 to \$12,025 per capita) and seven as high-income (per capita income above \$12,025). Thus, poverty alleviation is a major challenge, and improving infrastructure and developing trade links will promote growth and development in these areas.

Conclusion

As a result of the analysis of this study, the perspective program "One Belt, One Road" will have a significant and positive impact on Asian countries. For example, the improvement of transport corridors, general infrastructure and stabilization of trade processes in countries located along the program line could stabilize GDP growth in Central, Western and South Asia by 0.3 to 1.1 percent. It will also increase the countries economic development from 10.9 billion dollars to 89.7 billion dollars. The total export volume of the countries included in the perspective program can increase from 35 billion dollars to 130 billion dollars.

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